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**RELATIONSHIP OF IMMUNOLOGICAL PARAMETERS, ALLELIC
POLYMORPHISM OF CYTOKINE GENES AND DEGREE OF FIBROTIC LIVER
CHANGES IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC HEPATITIS C**

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Summary. Usychenko K. M. **RELATIONSHIP OF IMMUNOLOGICAL PARAMETERS, ALLELIC POLYMORPHISM OF CYTOKINE GENES AND DEGREE OF FIBROTIC LIVER CHANGES IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC HEPATITIS C.** It has now been established that the progression and outcomes of HCV-infection are influenced by many factors: an external factor (causative agent), the mechanism of development of the phenotype with the predominant influence of cytotoxic T-cells, regulatory T-cells (NK-cells), as well as the genotypic characteristics of the patient. Functional insufficiency of innate immunity is associated with the suppression of adaptive immunity cells – HCV specific CD8⁺ T-lymphocytes. In persistent viral infections, the phenotype of CD8⁺ T-specific cells is cleaved. At the same time, the functions of cytotoxicity and degranulation are preserved at the cellular level, and the production of cytokines is significantly inhibited. In recent years, it has been established that the most important place in the formation of the immune response belongs to the polymorphic genes of cytokines and the genes of their receptors. In this regard, research continues to identify genetic markers that are associated with the individual reactivity of the body to the effects of hepatitis C and B viruses, as well as predicting the rate of progression of fibrosis and the stability of the response to antiviral therapy. **The aim of the study** – determine the relationship between immune status, allele polymorphism genes of *IL-4* (*rs2243250*), *IL-10* (*rs1800896*), *TNF α* (*rs1800620*) and degree of liver fibrosis in patients with chronic hepatitis C. **Materials and methods.** The 100 patients with chronic hepatitis C aged 18 to 62 years were examined. The degree of liver fibrosis was established by Fibroscan. Molecular genetic studies included the determination of polymorphic variants of the *IL-4* (*rs2243250*), *IL-10* (*rs1800896*), *TNF α* (*rs1800620*) genes. Determination of subpopulations of T and B lymphocytes (CD3⁺, CD4⁺, CD8⁺, CD16⁺, CD19⁺) was carried out by the immunofluorescence method. The study of allelic polymorphism of *TNF α* (*rs1800620*), *IL-10* (*rs1800896*), *IL-4* (*rs2243250*) genes and immunological indexes revealed significant differences in the control and study groups of patients. Patients with the homozygous *CC IL-4* (*rs2243250*) genotype have less fibrotic changes in the liver than those with the homozygous *TT IL-4* (*rs2243250*) genotype. Patients with the homozygous *GG TNF α* (*rs1800620*) genotype have a lower degree of liver fibrosis than those with the homozygous *AA TNF α* (*rs1800620*) genotype. Patients with lesser changes in cellular immunity (decrease in CD3⁺, CD4⁺, CD16⁺, CD19⁺) have a lower degree of liver fibrosis. Patients with higher CD8⁺ levels had more pronounced liver fibrosis. The presence of a relationship between the degree of liver fibrosis and certain *IL-4* (*rs2243250*) and *TNF α* (*rs1800620*) genotypes makes it possible to use the obtained information as one of the criteria for the rapid progression of liver fibrotic processes. The severity of changes in cellular immunity is an additional criterion for the degree of morphological disorders in the liver tissue.

Key words: liver fibrosis, gene polymorphism, chronic hepatitis C, cell-mediated immunity

Реферат. Усиченко К. М. **ВЗАЄМОЗВ'ЯЗОК ІМУНОЛОГІЧНИХ ПАРАМЕТРІВ, АЛЕЛЬНОГО ПОЛІМОРФІЗМУ ГЕНІВ ЦИТОКІНІВ ТА СТУПЕНЯ ФІБРОТИЧНИХ ЗМІН ПЕЧІНКИ У ХВОРИХ НА ХРОНІЧНИЙ ГЕПАТИТ С.** – *Одеський національний медичний університет.* В даний час встановлено, що на прогресування і результати інфекції, викликані вірусом гепатиту С, впливає багато факторів: зовнішній фактор (збудник), механізм розвитку фенотипу з переважним впливом цитотоксичних Т-клітин, регуляторних Т-клітин (NK-клітин), а також генотипові характеристики пацієнта. Функціональна недостатність вродженого імунітету пов'язана з пригніченням клітин адаптивного імунітету – HCV специфічних CD8+ Т-лімфоцитів. При стійких вірусних інфекціях фенотип CD8+ Т-специфічних клітин розщеплюється. При цьому на клітинному рівні зберігаються функції цитотоксичності та дегрануляції, значно пригнічується продукція цитокінів. В останні роки встановлено, що найважливіше місце у формуванні імунної відповіді належить поліморфним генам цитокінів і генам їх рецепторів. У зв'язку з цим продовжуються дослідження з виявлення генетичних маркерів, які пов'язані з індивідуальною реактивністю організму на вплив вірусів гепатиту С і В, а також прогнозування швидкості прогресування фіброзу і стабільності відповіді на противірусну терапію. Мета дослідження – встановити зв'язок між імунним статусом, алельним поліморфізмом генів *IL-4* (*rs2243250*), *IL-10* (*rs1800896*), *TNFA* (*rs1800620*) та ступенем фіброзу печінки у хворих на хронічний гепатит С. Обстежено 100 хворих на хронічний гепатит С віком від 18 до 62 років. Ступінь фіброзу печінки встановлювали за допомогою Fibroscan. Молекулярно-генетичні дослідження включали визначення поліморфних варіантів генів *IL-4* (*rs2243250*), *IL-10* (*rs1800896*), *TNFA* (*rs1800620*). Визначення субпопуляцій Т- та В-лімфоцитів (CD3+, CD4+, CD8+, CD16+, CD19+) проводили методом імунофлюоресценції. Вивчення алельного поліморфізму генів *TNFA* (*rs1800620*), *IL-10* (*rs1800896*), *IL-4* (*rs2243250*) та імунологічних показників виявило певні відмінності в контрольній та основній групах пацієнтів. Пацієнти з гомозиготним генотипом *CC IL-4* (*rs2243250*) мають менше фіброзних змін у печінці, ніж у пацієнтів з гомозиготним генотипом *TT IL-4* (*rs2243250*). Пацієнти з гомозиготним генотипом *GG TNFA* (*rs1800620*) мають нижчий ступінь фіброзу печінки, ніж з гомозиготним генотипом *AA TNFA* (*rs1800620*). Пацієнти з меншими змінами клітинного імунітету (зниження CD3+, CD4+, CD16+, CD19+) мають менший ступінь фіброзу печінки, а пацієнти з вищим рівнем CD8+ мали більш виражений фіброз печінки. Наявність зв'язку між ступенем фіброзу печінки та певними генотипами *IL-4* (*rs2243250*) та *TNFA* (*rs1800620*) дає змогу використати отриману інформацію як один із критеріїв швидкого прогресування фіброзних процесів печінки. Виразність змін клітинного імунітету є додатковим критерієм ступеня морфологічних порушень у тканині печінки.

Ключові слова: фіброз печінки, поліморфізм генів, хронічний гепатит С, клітинний імунітет

Introduction

It has now been established that the progression and outcomes of HCV-infection are influenced by many factors: an external factor (causative agent), the mechanism of development of the phenotype with the predominant influence of cytotoxic T-cells, regulatory T-cells (NK-cells), as well as the genotypic characteristics of the patient [1, 2, 3].

One of the mechanisms of long-term persistence of a viral infection is the ability of virus hepatitis C to suppress the innate immunity, which leads to functional insufficiency of cells that play a major role in the elimination of causative agent - dendritic cells, macrophages, natural killers, and others [4, 5].

Functional insufficiency of innate immunity is associated with the suppression of adaptive immunity cells – HCV specific CD8+ T-lymphocytes. In persistent viral infections, the phenotype of CD8+ T-specific cells is cleaved. At the same time, the functions of cytotoxicity and degranulation are preserved at the cellular level, and the production of cytokines is significantly inhibited [6].

Obviously, a chronic infectious process develops as a result of violations in several

components of the immune system. It is known that among the factors of innate immunity, NK-cells play a key role in the elimination of viruses.

In addition, it was found that the most important function of NK-cells is the ability to produce cytokines IL-1, IL-2, IL-3, IL-8, TNF α , IFN α , β , γ , which allows us to regard these cells as the most important regulator of both innate and adaptive immunity [7, 8, 9].

One of the factors in the development of fibrosis is an intense T-killer response. Studies by a number of authors have shown a certain correlation between changes in the content and functional state of T-cells and the degree of fibrotic changes in the liver [10, 11, 12].

Studies of the characteristics of the immune response in patients with chronic hepatitis C have shown that the cellular immune response plays a leading role not only in the elimination of viruses, but also in the process of chronic HCV-infection.

In recent years, it has been established that the most important place in the formation of the immune response belongs to the polymorphic genes of cytokines and the genes of their receptors. In this regard, research continues to identify genetic markers that are associated with the individual reactivity of the body to the effects of hepatitis C and B viruses, as well as predicting the rate of progression of fibrosis and the stability of the response to antiviral therapy [13, 14, 15].

Thus, in the development of fibrogenesis, not only the genetic factors of hepatitis C and B viruses, but also the patient himself, are essential. At the same time, the course and outcomes of chronic viral hepatitis are probably influenced by the presence of polymorphism in not one, but several genes and a certain combination of them.

The aim of the study – determine the relationship between immune status, allele polymorphism genes of *IL-4* (*rs2243250*), *IL-10* (*rs1800896*), *TNF α* (*rs1800620*) and degree of liver fibrosis in patients with chronic hepatitis C.

Materials and methods

The 100 patients with chronic hepatitis C aged 18 to 62 years were examined. All examined patients were under monitoring in the hepatological center of the Odessa Municipal Clinical Infectious Diseases Hospital. Patients are residents of the Odessa region, in the study groups there were 53% of men and 47% of women. The duration of the disease was no more than 10 years.

The control group consisted of 30 practically healthy persons, the average age of which was 32 ± 1.05 years. The number of women and men was the same (15 people each).

All patients included in the study were given free and informed consent. The methodology of this investigation is in accordance with the requirements of the Committee on Bioethics of the Odesa National Medical University (protocol 179 of 19.11.2010).

Verification of the diagnosis of chronic hepatitis C included: routine biochemical tests (increased activity of AST and ALT, the increased level of bilirubin and the predominance of its direct fraction), serological markers (HCV-IgM, qualitative and quantitative detection HCV RNA).

The degree of liver fibrosis was established by Fibroscan. FibroScan is a non-invasive method for assessing the degree of liver fibrosis, which is implemented using a special apparatus. The FibroScan liver examination is based on the measurement of liver elasticity. The ultrasonic sensor of the instrument generates medium amplitude and low frequency oscillations. These vibrations pass through the skin, subcutaneous tissues and create in the liver.

Molecular genetic studies included the determination of polymorphic variants of the *IL-4* (*rs2243250*), *IL-10* (*rs1800896*), *TNF α* (*rs1800620*) genes. Polymorphism was studied by amplification of the corresponding regions of the genome by PCR. The structure of the primers used and the parameters of temperature cycles described in the literature and the genomic database. The studies were carried out on the basis of the German Diagnostic Center. St. Paul (Odesa).

Determination of subpopulations of T and B lymphocytes (CD3+, CD4+, CD8+, CD16+, CD19+) was carried out by the immunofluorescence method using a set of monoclonal and polyclonal antibodies to establish differential antigens of human lymphocytes on an Eurostar immunofluorescent microscope.

The obtained results of immunological studies were processed by the methods of variation statistics using the Excel program. The results are given as the arithmetic mean (M) and the arithmetic mean error ($\pm m$). In order to identify correlations between individual indicators, Spearman's correlation coefficient was applied. The distribution of genotypes for the studied

polymorphic loci was checked using Pearson's χ^2 test. The allele and genotype frequencies in the groups were compared using Pearson's χ^2 test with Yates' correction for continuity with the number of degrees of freedom equal to 1.

Research results and discussion

The study of allelic polymorphism of *TNFA* (*rs1800620*), *IL-10* (*rs1800896*), *IL-4* (*rs2243250*) genes revealed significant differences in the control and study groups of patients (Fig. 1-3).

Fig.1. Allelic polymorphism *IL-4* (*rs2243250*) in patients with chronic hepatitis C and healthy persons.

In healthy individuals, the homozygous *CC IL-4* (*rs2243250*) significantly predominated. In patients with chronic hepatitis C, its predominance was also noted, but to a much lesser extent ($p < 0.05$, $\chi^2 = 4.77$). In addition, the heterozygous genotype *CT IL-4* (*rs2243250*) was much more common in patients with chronic hepatitis C ($p < 0.05$, $\chi^2 = 6.78$).

Fig.2. Allelic polymorphism *IL-10* (*rs1800896*) in patients with chronic hepatitis C and healthy persons.

In healthy individuals, the homozygous genotype *CC IL-10* (*rs1800896*) prevailed ($p < 0.05$, $\chi^2 = 9.33$). In the study of polymorphism *IL-10* (*rs1800896*) in patients with chronic hepatitis C, the predominance of the heterozygous allele *GA IL-10* (*rs1800896*) was found in 53% of patients ($p < 0.05$, $\chi^2 = 6.44$).

Fig.3. Allelic polymorphism *TNFα* (*rs1800620*) genes in patients with chronic hepatitis C and healthy persons..

The studying of allelic polymorphism of *TNFα* (*rs1800620*) in the control group, the prevalence of the homozygous type of the *GG TNFα* (*rs1800620*) genotype was revealed in 91% ($p < 0.05$, $\chi^2 = 50.88$). In patients with chronic hepatitis C, the predominance of the heterozygous allele *GA TNFα* (*rs1800620*) (77%) ($p < 0.05$, $\chi^2 = 47.88$) was noted.

The results of the study of immunological status in patients with chronic hepatitis C and healthy persons are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Immunological parameters in patients with chronic hepatitis C and healthy persons (M±m).

Immunological parameter	Patients with chronic hepatitis C, n=100	Healthy persons, n = 30
1	2	3
Leukocytes, $10^9/\mu$	5,62±0,46	6,80±0,26
Lymphocytes, %	28,6±1,26*	31,2±1,04
Lymphocytes, abs.	1,58±0,03*	1,86±0,05
CD3+, abs.	1,18±0,04*	1,52±0,01
CD3+, %	32,29 ± 4,66*	71,8±1,92
CD4+, abs.	0,41±0,03*	0,78±0,06
CD4+, %.	27,97 ± 4,49*	41,2±1,5
CD8+, abs.	0,54±0,02*	0,48±0,02
CD8+, %.	24,07 ± 4,28*	20,5±1,3
CD16+, abs.	0,14±2,3*	0,22±0,02
CD16+, %	7,89 ± 2,70*	14,1±1,6
CD19+, abs.	0,28±0,16	0,24±0,19
CD19+, %.	15,29 ± 3,60*	10,8±1,2

• – the difference in indicators is significant in comparison with the indicators of healthy persons ($p < 0,05$).

Compared with healthy persons in patients with chronic hepatitis C, the level of CD3+ was 2.2 times lower, CD4+ - 1.5 times, CD16+ - 1.8 times: the content of CD8+ and CD19+ was increased - 1.2 times and 1.4 times, respectively. That is, patients with chronic hepatitis C have a significantly low content of CD3+, CD4+, CD16+ and an increase in the level of CD8+ and CD19+ compared to healthy people ($p < 0.05$).

A certain dependence of the general condition of patients and changes in immunological parameters was established. All patients with chronic hepatitis C complained of general weakness,

constant fatigue and loss of ability to work, but a certain part (43 people) emphasized that such changes in the general state not only do not allow them to work fully, but also force patients to radically change the world of their usual way of life. These patients had the lowest CD3+ (22-23%) and the highest CD8+ (28-29%).

All patients were divided into 3 groups in accordance with degree of liver fibrosis: with absent or minimal fibrosis (F0-F1) - 46%, moderate fibrosis (F2) - 31% and with severe fibrosis (F3) - 23%.

The relationship of fibrotic changes in the liver tissue, indicators of cellular immunity and allelic polymorphism of the studied genotypes was assessed using the Spearman rank correlation coefficient.

The presence of the following correlations has been established:

- a direct connection between the degree of fibrosis and *IL-4* (*rs2243250*) genotypes, $p < 0.01$ (a lower degree of fibrosis is noted in carriers of the CC *IL-4* (*rs2243250*) genotype, a greater degree of fibrosis in carriers of the TT *IL-4* (*rs2243250*) genotype);
- inverse connection between the degree of fibrosis and *TNF α* (*rs1800620*) genotypes, $p < 0.01$ (a lower degree of fibrosis is observed in carriers of the GG *TNF α* (*rs1800620*) genotype, a greater degree of fibrosis in carriers of the AA *TNF α* (*rs1800620*) genotype);
- inverse correlation between the degree of fibrosis and the relative content of CD3+, CD4+, CD16+, CD19+, $p < 0.01$ (patients with a greater degree of fibrosis have a lower content of the above cells);
- direct correlation between the degree of fibrosis and the relative content of CD8+, $p < 0.01$ (in patients with a greater degree of fibrosis, a higher content of these cells is noted).

The presence of a relationship between the degree of liver fibrosis and certain *IL-4* (*rs2243250*) and *TNF α* (*rs1800620*) genotypes makes it possible to use the obtained information as one of the criteria for the rapid progression of liver fibrotic processes. The severity of changes in cellular immunity is an additional criterion for the degree of morphological disorders in the liver tissue.

Conclusions

1. Patients with the homozygous CC *IL-4* (*rs2243250*) genotype have less fibrotic changes in the liver than those with the homozygous TT *IL-4* (*rs2243250*) genotype ($p < 0.01$).
2. Patients with the homozygous GG *TNF α* (*rs1800620*) genotype have a lower degree of liver fibrosis than those with the homozygous AA genotype ($p < 0.01$).
3. Patients with lesser changes in cellular immunity (decrease in CD3+, CD4+, CD16+, CD19+) have a lower degree of liver fibrosis ($p < 0.01$).
4. Patients with higher CD8+ levels had more pronounced liver fibrosis ($p < 0.01$).

Thus, an integrated approach to the examination of patients with chronic hepatitis C, using not only genetic, but also immunological criteria, will make it possible to get a more complete picture of the degree of changes in the liver tissue, to draw up individual criteria for the necessary therapy.

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СТРУКТУРНО-ДИНАМІЧНІ ОСОБЛИВОСТІ ШИЗОТИПОВОГО РОЗЛАДУ У ХВОРИХ ІЗ СУПУТНИМИ АФЕКТИВНИМИ ПОРУШЕННЯМИ

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Summary. Pliekhov V. A., Kurilo V. O. **STRUCTURAL-DYNAMIC FEATURES OF SCHIZOTYPAL DISORDER IN PATIENTS WITH COMORBID AFFECTIVE PATHOLOGY.** – State Medical University, Zaporizhzhia, Ukraine; e-mail: dgylia.as@gmail.com. **Background.** The study of the structural and dynamic features of the psychopathological symptoms of schizophrenia spectrum disorders remains one of the most